

Genocchi wavelet method for solving various types of conformable fractional differential equations

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ABSTRACT. In this paper, our purpose is to construct Genocchi wavelet functions (GWFs) and applied them for the numerical solution of various types of conformable fractional differential equations. Also, we present the operational matrices of GWFs, to reduce conformable fractional differential equations to a system of algebraic equations. In addition, we examine several examples to illustrate accuracy and efficiency of the proposed method.

Keywords: Genocchi wavelet functions, Operational matrix, Conformable fractional derivative, Fractional differential equations.

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1. Introduction

For the first time, conformable fractional derivative was proposed by Khalil et al. in [1], which is depending just on the basic limit definition of the derivative. Wavelet methods are a new numerical instrument for solving various kinds of fractional differential equations. Wavelets theory have attracted increasing attention from researchers and many works have been done in this topic, see for example [2, 3, 4].

2. Genocchi wavelets functions

We define the Genocchi wavelets $\psi_{nm}(t) = \psi(k, \hat{n}, m, t)$, which depends on four arguments, $\hat{n} = n - 1$, $n = 1, 2, \dots, 2^{k-1}$, k can assume any positive integer, m is the order for Genocchi polynomials and x is the normalized time. We introduce them on the interval $[0, 1)$ as follows:

$$(1) \quad \psi_{n,m}^h(t) = \begin{cases} 2^{\frac{k-1}{2}} \tilde{G}_m(2^{k-1}t - \hat{n}), & \frac{\hat{n}}{2^{k-1}} \leq t < \frac{\hat{n}+1}{2^{k-1}}, \\ 0, & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases} \quad m = 1, 2, \dots, M, \quad n = 1, 2, \dots, 2^{k-1},$$

with

$$(2) \quad \tilde{G}_m(2^{k-1}t - \hat{n}) = \begin{cases} 1, & m = 1, \\ \frac{1}{\sqrt{\frac{2^{h(-1)^m (m!)^2}{(2m)!} g_{2m}}} G_m(2^{k-1}t - \hat{n}), & m > 1. \end{cases}$$

where the coefficient $\frac{1}{\sqrt{\frac{2^{h(-1)^m (m!)^2}{(2m)!} g_{2m}}}$ is for normality and $G_m(t)$ are Genocchi polynomials [2].

2.1. Transformation matrix of Genocchi wavelets to Genocchi polynomials. In the present section, we expand Genocchi wavelets into an M -term Genocchi polynomials as [2]

$$(3) \quad \psi_{2^{k-1}M \times 1}(t) = \Theta_{2^{k-1}M \times M} G_{M \times 1}(t),$$

where transformation matrix of Genocchi wavelets functions to Genocchi polynomials Θ is obtained in general form by the following formula:

$$\Theta = \begin{cases} \Theta_1, & 0 \leq t < \frac{1}{2^{k-1}}, \\ \Theta_2, & \frac{1}{2^{k-1}} \leq t < \frac{2}{2^{k-1}}, \\ \vdots, & \vdots \\ \Theta_{2^{k-1}}, & \frac{\hat{n}}{2^{k-1}} \leq t < \frac{\hat{n}+1}{2^{k-1}}. \end{cases}$$

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So that, each element of Θ is introduced as follows:

$$\Theta_n = [O \quad O \quad \dots \quad \theta_n \quad \dots \quad O \quad O]^T, \quad \theta_n = [\theta_{ij}^n], \quad n = 1, 2, \dots, 2^{k-1}, \quad i, j = 1, 2, \dots, M,$$

$$\theta_{ij}^n = \begin{cases} 2^{i+\frac{k}{2}-\frac{3}{2}} \frac{1}{\lambda_i}, & i = j, \\ 2^{\frac{k-1}{2}-1} \frac{1}{\lambda_i(j!)} \left(G_i^{(j-1)}(2^{k-1}t - \hat{n})|_{t=0} + G_i^{(j-1)}(2^{k-1}t - \hat{n})|_{t=1} \right), & i > j, \\ 0, & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases}$$

$$\text{and } \lambda_i = \frac{1}{\sqrt{\frac{2^{(-1)^i(i!)^2}}{(2i)!} g_{2i}}}, \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, M.$$

2.2. Operational matrix of integer derivative. In order to construct the operational matrix of integer derivative for GWFs, we express the following relation:

$$(4) \quad \psi'(t) = \Phi\psi(t).$$

where Φ is the operational matrix of the integer derivative, which is defined in [2].

2.3. Pseudo-operational matrix of conformable fractional derivative. In this section, we introduced the pseudo-operational matrix of conformable fractional derivative as

$$(5) \quad {}_tT_\nu\psi(t) \simeq t^{1-\nu}\Upsilon\psi(t), \quad 0 < \nu \leq 1,$$

where Υ denotes the proposed matrix. First, we present the pseudo-operational matrix of conformable fractional derivative for Genocchi polynomials as follows:

$$(6) \quad \begin{aligned} {}_tT_\nu G_m(t) &= {}_tT_\nu \left(\sum_{k=0}^m \binom{m}{k} g_{m-k} t^k \right) = \sum_{k=0}^m \binom{m}{k} g_{m-k} k t^{k-\nu} = t^{1-\nu} \sum_{k=0}^m \binom{m}{k} g_{m-k} k t^{k-1} \\ &\simeq t^{1-\nu} \sum_{k=0}^m \binom{m}{k} g_{m-k} k \left(\sum_{i=0}^M a_i G_i(t) \right) = t^{1-\nu} \sum_{i=0}^M \left(\sum_{k=0}^m \binom{m}{k} g_{m-k} k a_i \right) G_i(t). \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, we have

$$(7) \quad {}_tT_\nu G(t) \simeq t^{1-\nu} \Lambda G(t).$$

From Eqs. (5) and (7), we get

$${}_tT_\nu\psi(t) = \Theta {}_tT_\nu G(t) \simeq t^{1-\nu} \Theta \Lambda G(t) = t^{1-\nu} \Theta \Lambda \Theta^{-1} \psi(t),$$

then $\Upsilon = \Theta \Lambda \Theta^{-1}$.

2.4. The pantograph operational matrix of GWFs. We construct the pantograph operational matrix of GWFs as [2]

$$(8) \quad \psi(qt) \simeq P_q \psi(t),$$

where the matrix P_q is called the pantograph operational matrix of GWFs.

3. Description of the proposed method

In this paper, we focus on the following conformable fractional differential equations:

$$(9) \quad {}_tT_\nu u(t) = F(t, u(t), u(qt), u'(t)), \quad 0 < \nu \leq 1, \quad q \in (0, 1),$$

Suppose that the unknown function $u(t)$ is approximated by GWFs as

$$(10) \quad u(t) \simeq A^T \psi(x),$$

then, according to matrices are presented in Eqs. (4), (5) and (8), we have

$$(11) \quad u'(t) \simeq A^T \Phi \psi(t), \quad {}_tT_\nu u(t) \simeq t^{1-\nu} A^T \Upsilon \psi(t), \quad u(qt) \simeq A^T P_q \psi(t),$$

Substituting Eqs. (10) and (11) in Eq. (9), we obtain a nonlinear algebraic equation. Then, by collocating the last equation at Newton-Cotes points [2, 7] and applied Newton's iterative method, we obtain the approximate solution.

REMARK 3.1. In [2], we estimate the upper bound of error for GWFs in the sense of Sobolev norm.

4. Illustrative examples

EXAMPLE 4.1. Consider the following conformable fractional Riccati equation:

$${}_tT_\nu u(t) = 2u(t) - u^2(t) + 1, \quad 0 < \nu \leq 1,$$

subject to initial condition $u(0) = 0$. The exact solution $\nu = 1$ is

$$u(t) = 1 + \sqrt{2} \tanh \left(\sqrt{2}t + \frac{1}{2} \ln \left(\frac{\sqrt{2} - 1}{\sqrt{2} + 1} \right) \right).$$

TABLE 1. Comparison of absolute errors of present method with methods in [3, 4] for $\nu = 1$ of Example 1.

t	Present method $M = 9, k = 2(\hat{m} = 18)$		Bernoulli wavelet method [3] $M = 10, k = 2(\hat{m} = 20)$	Chebyshev wavelet method [4] $\hat{m} = 192$
	Approximate solution	Absolute error		
0	0	0	0.000001	—
0.1	0.11029519595	9.6117×10^{-10}	0.110295	0.110311
0.2	0.24197679848	1.1406×10^{-9}	0.241977	0.241995
0.3	0.39510484735	1.3086×10^{-9}	0.395105	0.395123
0.4	0.56781216483	1.4595×10^{-9}	0.567812	0.567829
0.5	0.75601439062	2.8021×10^{-9}	0.756015	0.756029
0.6	0.95356621467	1.7992×10^{-9}	0.953566	0.953576
0.7	1.15294896520	1.7742×10^{-9}	1.152949	1.152955
0.8	1.34636365368	1.6871×10^{-9}	1.346364	1.346365
0.9	1.52691131173	1.5447×10^{-9}	1.526911	1.526909
1	1.68949839021	1.3754×10^{-9}	1.689497	1.689494

FIGURE 1. The approximate solution for different values of $\nu = 0.85, 0.9, 0.95, 1$ with $M = 7, k = 2$ of Example 1.

EXAMPLE 4.2. Consider the fractional nonlinear pantograph differential equation:

$${}_tT_\nu u(t) = 1 - 2u^2\left(\frac{t}{2}\right), \quad 0 < \nu \leq 1, \quad 0 < t \leq 1,$$

$$u(t) = \sin(t), \quad -1 \leq t \leq 0,$$

subject to initial condition $u(0) = 1$. The exact solution $\nu = 1$ is $u(t) = \sin(t)$.

TABLE 2. Comparison of absolute errors of present method with methods in [5, 6] for $\nu = 1$ of Example 2.

t	Present method		Modified Chebyshev wavelet method [5]	Legendre wavelet method [6]
	$M = 9, k = 1$	$M = 9, k = 2$	$M = 9, k = 1$	$M = 9, k = 2$
0	0	0	0	0
0.125	2.1512×10^{-13}	6.3524×10^{-16}	1.7070×10^{-12}	2.3852×10^{-9}
0.25	2.0996×10^{-13}	1.3207×10^{-15}	2.4732×10^{-12}	2.2545×10^{-9}
0.375	1.9072×10^{-13}	1.9800×10^{-15}	9.3642×10^{-12}	2.0860×10^{-9}
0.5	1.6853×10^{-13}	1.9749×10^{-16}	1.7877×10^{-11}	1.6042×10^{-9}
0.625	1.4078×10^{-13}	1.1161×10^{-12}	1.8884×10^{-11}	1.9404×10^{-9}
0.75	1.0508×10^{-13}	1.7153×10^{-12}	3.0427×10^{-12}	1.0233×10^{-9}
0.875	7.4017×10^{-14}	2.0261×10^{-12}	1.6443×10^{-12}	1.2360×10^{-9}
1	2.4286×10^{-13}	2.1221×10^{-12}	4.5108×10^{-10}	8.0780×10^{-10}

TABLE 3. Errors various values of M, k with $\nu = 1$ of Example 2.

	$k = 1$			$k = 2$		
	$M = 2$	$M = 4$	$M = 7$	$M = 2$	$M = 4$	$M = 7$
l_2 -error	5.8690×10^{-4}	2.4364×10^{-6}	4.6617×10^{-10}	7.9783×10^{-4}	5.6194×10^{-6}	1.5697×10^{-9}
l_∞ -error	2.9236×10^{-4}	1.2443×10^{-6}	1.9953×10^{-10}	4.4197×10^{-4}	3.0309×10^{-6}	8.4655×10^{-10}

TABLE 4. Errors for various values of ν with $M = 9, k = 1$ of Example 2.

	$\nu = 0.9$	$\nu = 0.99$	$\nu = 0.999$	$\nu = 0.9999$	$\nu = 1$
l_∞ -error	7.4144×10^{-2}	7.0318×10^{-3}	6.9911×10^{-4}	6.9870×10^{-6}	2.4286×10^{-13}

5. Conclusion

A general formulation for the Genocchi wavelet functions has been derived. The main advantages of proposed method is that with a small number of the GWFs are needed to obtain a satisfactory result. Also, examples are demonstrate the efficiency of the mentioned method.

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